

From mechanism to model: understanding intracellular positive-sense RNA virus replication through quantitative frameworks

Caroline I. Larkin^{1,2}, Alexander A. DiBiasi¹, William B. Klimstra^{3,4}, and James R. Faeder^{1*}

1 Department of Computational and Systems Biology, University of Pittsburgh School of Medicine, Pittsburgh, PA, United States of America

2 Current address: Department of Immunology, University of Pittsburgh School of Medicine, Pittsburgh, PA, United States of America

3 Center for Vaccine Research, University of Pittsburgh School of Medicine, Pittsburgh, PA, United States of America

4 Department of Immunology, University of Pittsburgh School of Medicine, Pittsburgh, PA, United States of America

* E-mail: faeder@pitt.edu

Abstract

Positive-sense single-stranded RNA viruses (+ssRNA) represent a major class of human pathogens, including SARS-CoV-2, hepatitis C virus, and Dengue virus, which pose enormous burdens on public health systems globally. Despite sharing the same genome type, +ssRNA viruses utilize diverse replication strategies resulting in highly variable dynamics. Mechanistic modeling has proven invaluable for probing the intricate interactions underlying viral replication and linking them to infection outcomes. Here we review mechanistic models describing the replication cycle of pathogenic +ssRNA viruses and their contributions to our understanding. We identify five key areas where models have advanced knowledge: genome allocation strategies across replication processes, exploitation of host cell resources, regulation of transcription between viral RNA strands, virus-host immune interactions, and therapeutic target identification. Models reveal that +ssRNA viruses face critical tradeoffs in allocating their genome between transcription, translation, and assembly, with different viruses employing distinct strategies based on replication speed and dissemination within and between host cells. Host factors, particularly ribosomes and membrane structures, emerge as critical determinants of infection outcomes. The complex interplay between viral antagonism and host innate immunity significantly influences viral clearance, with timing and magnitude of interferon responses being crucial. Consistently across multiple virus types, targeting viral translation and RNA synthesis processes is a potent aspect of the innate immune response and has proven most effective for therapeutic intervention. We conclude that mechanistic modeling, when combined with experimental validation, provides essential insights for understanding +ssRNA virus biology. These insights are critical for developing antiviral strategies.

Introduction

Over a third of all virus genera are positive-sense single-stranded RNA viruses (+ssRNA) [1], representing a diverse class of infectious agents with highly variable

genome sizes, structures, and pathologies. Many are highly pathogenic in humans, including SARS-CoV-2, hepatitis C virus (HCV), Dengue virus, and Eastern equine encephalitis virus, causing diseases ranging from acute respiratory infections to chronic liver disease and death. These infections place significant strain on public health systems globally. For example, HCV affects tens of millions of people worldwide [2], Dengue causes nearly 400 million infections annually (with around 100 million symptomatic cases and tens of thousands of deaths) [3,4], and the COVID-19 pandemic has imposed economic costs ranging from tens of billions to trillions of dollars [5,6].

Mechanistic modeling has been instrumental for understanding viral infections by enabling hypothesis testing and therapeutic target identification *in silico* [7,8]. While population-level models like the target cell-limited (TCL) framework [9] have successfully described viral dynamics across cell populations, they rely on the simplifying assumption of uniform particle production rates across infected cells. This assumption, however, is challenged by experimental studies revealing that viral progeny production can vary by several orders of magnitude within cells of the same strain and across individual hosts [10–12]. This remarkable heterogeneity underscores the need for mechanistic models that explicitly capture the intracellular dynamics of +ssRNA virus replication.

In this review, we highlight how mechanistic modeling of intracellular +ssRNA virus replication has advanced our understanding of viral biology over the past several decades. Rather than providing an exhaustive catalog, we focus on five key areas (Fig. 1) where models have yielded particularly valuable insights: A) genome allocation strategies across replication processes, B) exploitation of host cell resources, C) transcription regulation between viral RNA strands, D) virus-antiviral host interactions, and E) therapeutic target identification. Through this thematic approach, we demonstrate that mechanistic modeling—particularly when integrated with experimental validation—has become an important tool for understanding +ssRNA virus biology and developing effective antiviral strategies.

+ssRNA virus replication basics

Despite their genomic diversity, all +ssRNA viruses follow a conserved six-step replication cycle: 1) attachment, 2) entry, 3) uncoating, 4) replication, 5) assembly, and 6) export (Fig. 2). A defining feature of these viruses is that their positive-sense genome can be directly translated by host ribosomes to synthesize viral proteins, most notably the RNA-dependent RNA polymerase (RdRp), which has no ortholog in eukaryotic cells. The RdRp subsequently generates a negative-sense template strand from the infecting genome, which serves as the template for producing additional genome copies as well as subgenomic mRNAs, if encoded in the genome. Newly synthesized genomes and viral proteins are subsequently assembled into progeny particles that exit the cell through budding with enveloped viruses or direct virion release with non-enveloped viruses [13].

Central to understanding +ssRNA virus replication is the formation of specialized replication organelles (ROs), which involve rearrangements of host cellular membranes derived from the endoplasmic reticulum (ER), Golgi apparatus, or plasma membrane [14–16]. These membrane-bounded compartments serve multiple functions: they create a protective environment that shields viral components from host immune surveillance, while also concentrating replication machinery and host cell macromolecules to enhance the efficiency of RNA synthesis [17,18].

Although the basic replication steps are conserved, +ssRNA viruses display diverse kinetic replication profiles that reflect their distinct ecological niches and pathogenic strategies (Fig. 3). At one extreme, alphaviruses such as Eastern equine encephalitis virus (EEEV), typically replicate rapidly, producing infectious progeny within 3–4 hours

Fig 1. Major themes across published papers of the +ssRNA viral replication cycle. Examples of five key areas of mechanistic modeling research are illustrated: (A) Genome allocation strategies examining the tradeoffs between transcription, translation, and assembly processes; (B) Host resource exploitation focusing on ribosome and membrane availability; (C) Transcription regulation including RNA strand ratios and replication modes; (D) Virus-immune system interactions and antagonism mechanisms; (E) Therapeutic strategies including broad-spectrum and direct-acting antivirals.

post-infection [19]. In contrast, Dengue virus (DENV) follows an intermediate trajectory with particle production occurring over 15–30 hours, while hepatitis C virus (HCV) establishes persistent, low-level chronic infections [20, 21]. These temporal differences have implications for pathogenesis, dissemination and transmission, and opportunities for therapeutic intervention.

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Fig 2. General steps of positive-sense RNA virus replication within a cell. Illustration of the six conserved steps of positive-sense RNA virus replication within a cell.

Fig 3. Infectious particle (PFU) production dynamics of various +ssRNA viruses. Infectious particle (PFU) production, also referred to as virus titer, for representative +ssRNA viruses. Data for Dengue virus, Coxsackievirus B3, and hepatitis C virus are taken from [21]. Data for SARS-CoV and SARS-CoV-2 viruses are taken from [22]. EEEV data from [19]. MOI, multiplicity of infection.

Viral RNA allocation to different replicative processes

Due to the requirements of +ssRNA viruses for host macromolecules to carry out most replication processes, one of the fundamental challenges facing +ssRNA viruses is the optimal distribution of their limited genomic resources across competing replicative processes. Each viral genome must simultaneously fulfill three critical functions: serve as mRNA for translation of essential viral proteins, a template for transcription to produce negative-sense RNA strands, and provide the genetic material for assembly into progeny viral particles. This creates an intricate balancing act where misallocation can

have significant consequences. For example, insufficient allocation of genomes to transcription could result in inadequate production of negative-sense templates, ultimately constraining RNA replication and progeny production. Understanding how different +ssRNA viruses have evolved distinct allocation strategies not only clarifies the mechanistic basis of their diverse replication kinetics but also identifies potential vulnerabilities that can be exploited for antiviral intervention.

Genome allocation and progeny yield

The theoretical basis for genome allocation was established by Krakauer and Komarova (2003), who analyzed this problem using a five-reaction kinetic model [23]. Their framework captured the competition between genome binding to viral proteins for transcription, ribosomal binding for translation, and incorporation into progeny particles during assembly. Steady-state analysis revealed a key constraint on sustainable viral production: the rate of assembly must not exceed the rate of transcription complex formation. This principle showed that viruses prioritizing immediate progeny production through excessive allocation to assembly ultimately compromise their long-term replicative capacity. This framework has since served as the foundation for many mechanistic models.

Building on this work, Nakabayashi (2012) applied these concepts to HCV replication dynamics [24]. Using a compartmental model that distinguished between cytoplasmic translation and replication organelle-based transcription, this study demonstrated a positive correlation between transcription-to-assembly allocation ratios and overall particle production. The results suggested that HCV's characteristic low-level persistence arises from an evolutionary strategy favoring genome allocation to assembly over transcription.

This conclusion was supported by McLean et al. (2010), who approached the allocation problem differently [25]. Rather than using fixed allocation parameters, the authors simulated various genome allocation strategies by modulating model parameters and measuring resulting progeny particle yield. Despite this methodological difference, their results converged on the same insight: HCV has evolved an assembly-dominant allocation strategy as a mechanism for maintaining chronic infection.

The most comprehensive comparative analysis came from Zitzmann et al. (2023), who developed a generalized framework to study HCV, coxsackievirus B3 (CVB3), and DENV [21]. This study showed how allocation strategies map onto viral lifestyles: the fast-replicating CVB3 employed a transcription-dominant strategy consistent with rapid genome amplification; chronic HCV maintained its assembly preference; and DENV displayed a dynamic strategy, shifting from transcription-dominant during acute phases to assembly-dominant during later phases. This temporal flexibility suggests that allocation is not a fixed trait but can evolve in response to selective pressures tied to replication speed and host transmission requirements.

While Zitzmann et al.(2023) examined allocation of full-length RNA species, another study presented a model to elucidate how genome allocation produces various genomic RNA subspecies and how this impacts +ssRNA viral replication dynamics [26]. In particular, the authors account for the synthesis of defective-interfering (DI) genomes, defined as mutated viral genomes that cannot replicate autonomously but may nonetheless be incorporated into progeny virions [27]. With this model, the authors explored the competitive dynamics among RNA species and their consequences on progeny yield. This framework demonstrated that the balance between DI RNA production with the relative ratio of viral RNA degradation and synthesis is the critical determinant of complete viral clearance. These findings highlight the need for future studies to quantify and mechanistically characterize interactions between viral and DI

RNA, which may offer novel avenues to exploit endogenous interference dynamics in the development of antiviral strategies.

Tradeoffs in allocation strategies at the population level

The allocation strategies observed within individual cells take on added complexity when considered in the context of viral population dynamics. Krakauer and Komarova's multiscale analysis revealed an evolutionary tension that shapes replication strategies [23]: while efficient intracellular replication favors transcription-dominant allocation to maximize genome amplification, efficient cell-to-cell transmission favors assembly-dominant allocation to ensure progeny production. This creates an inherent tradeoff that different viruses resolve in distinct ways.

This theoretical prediction was supported experimentally by Iwanami et al. (2020), who compared two HCV strains with distinct replication characteristics [28]. The strain producing more viral particles allocated 2.7-fold more genomic resources to assembly, achieving greater cell-to-cell transmission but at the cost of reduced intracellular genome amplification. This study illustrates how computational models can anticipate and explain experimental outcomes.

Together, these studies indicate that +ssRNA viruses have evolved diverse solutions to the genome allocation problem, reflecting distinct ecological pressures. Fast-replicating viruses tend to optimize for rapid intracellular amplification through transcription-focused allocation, whereas viruses that exhibit persistent replication prioritize sustained transmission via particle production through assembly-dominant strategies. This diversity highlights the value of flexible modeling frameworks that allow allocation strategies to emerge from parameter fitting rather than being imposed *a priori*.

Host resource constraints on viral replication

While genome allocation strategies determine how viruses distribute their genetic material, the success of any replication strategy ultimately depends on the availability of host cell resources that viruses must exploit. Further, viruses can antagonize host cell macromolecular synthesis, thereby depleting the pool of host resources available within the cell, ultimately limiting viral replication. Mechanistic models have consistently shown that the availability of host resources strongly influences viral particle production, often in nonlinear ways that introduce unexpected constraints and opportunities [29–31].

Andreu-Moreno et al. demonstrated that while viral replication rates initially scale with the concentration of infecting genomes, this relationship breaks down beyond a critical threshold where host resource depletion becomes the rate-limiting factor [31]. This finding illustrates a broader principle: viral success is constrained not only by the efficiency of viral processes but also by the finite capacity of the host cell environment. Zitzmann et al. (2020) found that delayed depletion of host factors during particle assembly best captured HCV replication data, suggesting that host factors are rate-limiting for progeny export [32]. Binder et al. (2013) systematically tested host factor involvement across eight replication steps and identified replication organelle (RO) formation and negative-strand synthesis initiation as most host factor-dependent [29]. Host factor concentrations were 10-fold higher in permissive cell lines, explaining observed RNA concentration differences. Applying a similar framework to DENV, Zitzmann et al. (2020) found that immune-competent cells had more host factors for RO formation and RNA synthesis but became assembly-limited, explaining lower particle production despite higher RNA levels [30]. Together, these studies

indicate that host factor availability enhances RNA replication but can simultaneously limit particle production.

Ribosomes

Among the host resources that viruses must exploit, ribosomes occupy a central position as the cellular machinery responsible for protein synthesis. During infection, individual RNA strands often recruit multiple ribosomes simultaneously to form polysomes, amplifying protein production [33,34]. The first systematic attempt to model polysomes was undertaken by Dahari et al. (2007) in their study of HCV replication [35]. By comparing simultaneous versus sequential ribosome binding, they found that the simpler simultaneous binding model was sufficient to reproduce experimental RNA concentrations. This work established the framework that was adopted by subsequent models of viral translation.

Despite this early foundation, the optimal approach to modeling polysome dynamics remains debated. Regoes et al. incorporated sequential binding with fixed delays between recruitment events [36], whereas Lopacinski et al. retained the simultaneous binding framework but scaled rates by ribosome number [37]. More recently, Larkin et al. extended these approaches by explicitly modeling ribosome packing and polysome spacing on viral RNA during EEEV infection [19]. Their analysis demonstrated that ribosome spacing was a critical determinant of particle production, with denser packing required to sustain the extreme replication kinetics of alphaviruses. This study illustrates how moving beyond simplified binding schemes toward biophysically explicit representations of polysomes can reveal novel constraints on viral replication.

Across studies, a consistent conclusion has emerged: ribosome availability is a critical bottleneck that influences both protein translation and RNA replication, since RNA synthesis depends on viral protein production [21,36,38,39]. For example, Zitzmann et al. showed that ribosome availability had stronger effects on viral RNA dynamics than any other model parameter examined [21]. Their comparative analysis also revealed large differences in estimated ribosome concentrations across HCV, DENV, and CVB3, suggesting that different viruses may have evolved distinct strategies for competing with host cells for this limited resource.

These findings point to ribosomes as central determinants of viral replication, while also highlighting gaps in current knowledge. The quantitative impact of polysome formation on viral translation kinetics remains poorly characterized, as does the mechanistic basis of variability in ribosome availability across virus-host systems. Addressing these questions will require more advanced experimental measurements coupled with translation modeling frameworks that capture the dynamic competition between host and viral processes.

Replication organelles

Beyond ribosomes, the reorganization of cellular membranes into replication organelles (ROs) represents another key interface between viral replication and host resources. Computational modeling of ROs was introduced by Dahari et al. (2007), who treated them as specialized transcription compartments distinct from cytoplasmic sites of translation and assembly [35]. This two-compartment model became a standard architecture for subsequent studies. However, their analysis produced a counterintuitive prediction: removing ROs increased steady-state RNA levels. Binder et al. later confirmed this effect, suggesting that ROs might not act as accelerators of replication but rather as regulatory structures that coordinate RNA and protein production by limiting negative-strand initiation [29].

This regulatory role was extended by Nakabayashi, who analyzed how genome trafficking between ROs and the cytoplasm influences replication efficiency [24]. High genome export ratios arrested particle production due to the depletion of genomes available for RNA synthesis, providing a mechanistic explanation for HCV’s slow viral production kinetics. The model suggested that HCV allocates genomes preferentially to the cytoplasm early in infection, creating a bottleneck that supports chronic, low-level replication.

Lopacinski et al. tested three potential RO functions in CVB3—immune shielding, RNA protection, and machinery concentration [37]. Only machinery concentration was essential for recapitulating experimental data, indicating that this is the primary function for accelerating replication kinetics. Chhajer et al. explicitly modeled RO formation dynamics across HCV, poliovirus, and Japanese encephalitis virus [40], showing that RO formation rate is tightly coupled to replication efficiency across viruses, underscoring its importance for both fast and slow replicators and its potential as a therapeutic target.

More recently, spatially explicit modeling has opened new perspectives on RO function. Knodel et al. introduced an “In Silico Microscopes” framework for HCV, coupling surface- and volume-based partial differential equations to capture ER membrane geometry, membranous web formation, and host factor diffusion [41]. Their analysis demonstrated that spatial constraints in host factor supply and RNA diffusion produce replication dynamics that diverge from well-mixed assumptions, highlighting the importance of cell geometry in shaping infection outcomes.

Together, these advances show that ROs are more than passive replication sites: they act as regulators of strand synthesis, concentrators of machinery, and spatially constrained hubs where ribosome recruitment, RNA diffusion, and host factor availability intersect. The integration of spatial and mechanistic detail in recent models suggests that therapeutic strategies could exploit not only the kinetics of viral enzymes but also the geometric and resource-limited nature of the replication environment.

Transcription regulation

The regulation of viral RNA synthesis represents another critical layer of control in +ssRNA virus replication. Whereas genome allocation strategies determine how viral RNA is distributed across competing processes, transcriptional regulation defines how genomes are amplified and maintained within infected cells. Differences in transcriptional programs influence both short-term replication efficiency and long-term evolutionary trajectories by shaping mutation accumulation and genetic diversity. Two major themes have emerged from mechanistic modeling in this area: the characteristic ratios of positive- to negative-sense RNA strands and the replication modes that govern how progeny genomes are synthesized. Together, these features provide complementary insights into how viruses balance efficient replication with adaptability.

RNA strand ratios

The relative abundance of positive- and negative-sense RNA strands is a key determinant of viral replication dynamics and fitness. Positive strands must serve simultaneously as templates for protein translation and assembly into new virions, while negative strands are essential intermediates for genome amplification. The ratio of these two forms therefore reflects how a virus balances competing demands for replication, protein synthesis, and packaging, and directly influences both replication efficiency and evolutionary potential. Because of this, positive-to-negative strand ratios are often treated as molecular signatures of viral replication strategies.

Across +ssRNA viruses, strand ratios strongly favor positive-sense accumulation, but the precise values vary widely across families and can shift dynamically depending on the infection context (Table 1).

Table 1. Positive-to-negative sense RNA ratios of +ssRNA viruses.

Virus/Virus Category	Positive-to-negative sense RNA Ratio	Reference(s)
Poliovirus	15-50:1	[42–46]
HCV	10:1	[47–49]
CVB3	40-100:1	[50]
Alphaviruses	10-20:1	[13, 51]
Coronaviruses	100:1	[52]

These ratios are shaped by factors such as the relative initiation rates of positive- and negative-strand promoters and the functional state of the viral RdRp. Alphaviruses illustrate this temporal regulation via proteolytic cleavage events that create an irreversible functional switch in the replication machinery from negative-strand to positive-strand synthesis [20]. Experimentally resolving these dynamics remains challenging due to the presence of double-stranded RNA intermediates, assay sensitivity limits, and potential cross-contamination in strand-specific assays.

Given these challenges, mechanistic models have been essential for quantifying and interpreting strand ratio dynamics. Dahari et al. used their HCV model to explain why this virus consistently maintains a 10:1 ratio, showing that RdRp binding to negative-strand templates must occur about 200-fold faster than to positive strands [35]. Grebennikov et al. applied sensitivity analysis to SARS-CoV-2, finding that translation rates, positive-strand replication rates, and early steps such as fusion and uncoating contribute to its higher 100:1 ratio [53]. Regoes et al. showed that poliovirus’s observed ratio closely matched the model-predicted optimum for maximizing viral growth [36]. Together, these studies demonstrate that RNA strand ratios are not fixed traits but dynamic outcomes of replication strategy, and that models provide critical insight into how these ratios emerge from underlying biochemical processes.

This principle was further illustrated in a detailed model of EEEV replication, which showed that maintaining the high positive-to-negative strand ratio characteristic of alphaviruses required both sufficient ribosome numbers and dense ribosome packing on viral RNA [19]. This result directly links host translational capacity to strand ratio regulation and underscores the importance of explicitly representing ribosome density in mechanistic models.

Replication modes

Replication mode describes how many RNA strands are synthesized from a template. Two paradigms exist: Stamping Machine Replication (SMR), where all progeny are one generation from the original [54], and Geometric Replication (GR), where iterative rounds produce multi-generational progeny [55]. Both modes occur in nature [56, 57].

The replication mode has major implications for mutation accumulation and viral fitness because it determines how errors introduced by the RdRp are propagated. High RdRp mutation rates, ranging from 1 in every 10^3 to 10^6 nucleotides [58–61], generate so-called quasispecies—populations of diverse but related genomes [62, 63]—that enable rapid adaptation to selective pressures. In SMR, all progeny are one generation from the original template, so mutations arise independently in each genome but are not further amplified. This limits the accumulation of deleterious mutations and provides robustness at high mutation rates. In contrast, GR allows progeny genomes to serve as templates for subsequent rounds of replication. As a result, mutations are inherited and

propagated across generations, compounding their effects. While this increases susceptibility to deleterious mutation loads, it also generates greater genetic diversity, which can enhance adaptability under changing conditions.

Sardanyés et al. found that SMR produces strand ratios consistent with experimental observations and is more robust to deleterious mutations than GR, which leads to extinction at high mutation rates [64]. Thébaud et al. similarly showed that SMR is optimal for viral amplification and increasingly favored at higher mutation rates [65]. In contrast, Schulte et al. calibrated a poliovirus model to experimental data and found evidence for GR with progeny approximately five generations from the original genome [66]. This suggests that poliovirus accepts greater mutation risk in exchange for increased genetic diversity.

Overall, models indicate that SMR enhances robustness to deleterious mutations, while GR promotes genetic diversity. Poliovirus appears to employ GR, possibly to enhance adaptability despite higher mutation susceptibility. Further modeling of replication modes in other +ssRNA viruses will help clarify how these strategies contribute to viral evolution.

Innate immune interactions

While transcriptional regulation reflects how viruses control their own genome amplification, these processes are further shaped by host defenses. In contrast to the passive constraints imposed by limited host resources, the innate immune system represents an active cellular machinery that directly interferes with viral replication.

The innate immune system serves as the first line of defense, employing pattern recognition receptors to detect pathogen-associated molecular patterns (PAMPs), such as viral RNA, and trigger interferon (IFN) expression [67, 68]. This response cascades through downstream ISG production to establish an antiviral state. Because clearance requires a balance between effective defense and avoiding excessive inflammation, both timing and magnitude are critical [69]. +ssRNA viruses counter this pressure through antagonism mechanisms that disrupt key signaling nodes: HCV cleaves mitochondrial antiviral-signaling protein (MAVS) [70], dengue virus inhibits I κ B kinase ϵ (IKK ϵ) [71], SARS-CoV-2 degrades type I interferon receptor (IFNAR1) [72], and EEEV can block STAT1 phosphorylation and restrict host macromolecular synthesis, suppressing upregulation of antiviral effectors [73].

With respect to the timing of immune sensing, Zitzmann et al. developed a DENV-immune model that incorporated RNA sensing, IFN/ISG expression, and viral antagonism within a single framework [30]. Model calibration to immune-competent and immune-deficient cell lines revealed that the innate immune system primarily targets translation initiation, a finding supported for numerous viruses [74], while viral antagonism suppresses IFN and ISG expression by more than 88%. Their analysis further demonstrated that the timing of RNA sensing, rather than its efficacy, was the critical determinant of viral clearance.

In terms of the magnitude of IFN responses, Castaño-Arcila et al. applied a stochastic DENV model incorporating ISG responses to quantify IFN levels [75]. They identified 35 IU/mL as the minimum dose for potential clearance and 105 IU/mL for consistent clearance. Intermediate doses produced bistable outcomes, showing how models can predict treatment success or failure depending on IFN concentration.

The predictive power of these approaches extends beyond dosage optimization to mechanism identification. Lopacinski et al. exemplified this by combining CVB3 modeling with experimental validation to identify MAVS cleavage as the specific viral antagonism mechanism [37]. Their model made the surprising prediction that viral antagonism effectiveness was timing-sensitive, with 5-fold immune resistance enabling

clearance regardless of IFN timing. This finding demonstrates how coupled virus-immune models can not only explain observed phenomena but also guide targeted experiments to identify specific molecular mechanisms.

Most recently, Boddepalli et al. developed the most comprehensive integration to date of viral life cycle and innate immune dynamics, combining detailed (+)RNA virus replication with RIG-I-mediated sensing and JAK-STAT signaling [76]. Their systematic analysis revealed a sharp infection threshold—termed the Viral-Immune Transition Boundary—where minor variations in immune strength or viral antagonism capacity determine bimodal outcomes between viral clearance and persistent infection. Remarkably, they identified ISG mRNA translation efficiency and viral replication kinetics as the primary molecular determinants of infection fate, explaining why Japanese Encephalitis virus experiences 182-fold suppression by the immune response compared to only 3.4-fold for HCV. The model also elucidated IFN desensitization mechanisms, pinpointing receptor-TYK2 complex depletion as the key bottleneck that limits cellular responsiveness to repeated IFN exposure.

Collectively, these modeling efforts reveal that rapid IFN induction timing emerges as the single most critical factor determining viral clearance success. Beyond this mechanistic insight, coupled virus-immune models have proven remarkably effective at predicting viral behavior under diverse immune conditions and guiding experimental identification of molecular antagonism mechanisms, thereby providing a robust computational framework for identifying treatment targets that enhance innate immune responses.

Developing therapeutic strategies *in silico*

The interplay between viral replication and host immune responses highlights numerous points of vulnerability in the +ssRNA replication cycle. Translating these mechanistic insights into therapeutic strategies has increasingly relied on computational modeling, which allows systematic evaluation of intervention points and drug mechanisms without the prohibitive costs of exhaustive experimental testing. In this section, we review how mechanistic models have been applied to identify broad-spectrum antiviral targets and to evaluate direct-acting antivirals at both the molecular and cellular levels.

Broad-spectrum targets

The complexity of +ssRNA virus replication creates numerous potential therapeutic targets, but identifying the most effective intervention points requires rigorous analysis. Sensitivity analysis provides a powerful computational approach for determining which model parameters most significantly impact viral particle production, thereby guiding rational antiviral development [77]. This mathematical framework enables comprehensive *in silico* therapeutic evaluation, accelerating treatment optimization by eliminating the need for costly and time-consuming experimental screening.

When Zitzmann et al. applied this approach to DENV replication, they discovered that polyprotein cleavage, RNA synthesis, and replication organelle formation emerged as the most critical control points [30]. Building on this foundation, their systematic evaluation of simulated interventions revealed that strategies targeting translation initiation, elongation, and RNA synthesis demonstrated the highest clearance potential among all tested approaches.

The robustness of these findings became apparent when the same research group expanded their analysis to develop a generalized model encompassing HCV, DENV, and CVB3 [21]. This cross-virus comparison confirmed that translation and RNA synthesis inhibition remained the most effective therapeutic strategies across all three viral

systems. However, the analysis also revealed important nuances: intervention timing proved especially critical for the fast-replicating CVB3, while combination therapies consistently outperformed single-target approaches, though they required significantly higher individual drug efficacies to achieve meaningful antiviral effects.

These computational predictions have found strong support across diverse modeling efforts. Independent SARS-CoV-2 models developed by multiple research groups similarly identified translation and RNA synthesis as the most promising therapeutic targets [39, 53], reinforcing the importance of these processes in +ssRNA replication control.

A complementary analysis of EEEV dynamics reached a similar conclusion: sensitivity analysis identified transcription parameters as the most influential determinants of infectious particle production [19]. Together with results from DENV, HCV, CVB3, and SARS-CoV-2, these findings highlight the consistent emergence of RNA synthesis as a central vulnerability across diverse +ssRNA viruses.

The convergence of evidence across multiple +ssRNA virus models—spanning DENV, HCV, CVB3, and SARS-CoV-2—demonstrates that translation and RNA synthesis consistently emerge as the most critical targets for broad-spectrum antiviral strategies. While combination therapies prove most effective in computational simulations, their clinical success will depend on achieving sufficiently high individual drug efficacies to realize their theoretical potential.

Direct-acting antivirals

Moving beyond broad-spectrum targets, mechanistic models have proven equally powerful for evaluating specific antiviral compounds and elucidating their molecular mechanisms of action. When integrated with population-level frameworks, intracellular models can comprehensively characterize therapeutic pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics by capturing the critical cell-to-cell heterogeneity in drug effects that often determines treatment success or failure.

The versatility of this modeling approach is exemplified by studies of immune-targeted therapies. Castaño-Arcila et al. leveraged DENV modeling to evaluate ISG-targeted gene therapies, discovering that IFITM2 or ISG20 upregulation could achieve greater than 95% viral clearance in combination with a IFN dose of 40 IU/mL compared to the 100 IU/mL dosage required for interferon therapy alone [75]. This finding suggests that targeted ISG enhancement could improve therapeutic efficacy while reducing the interferon dosages that often cause problematic side effects [78–80].

The critical importance of timing in IFN-based interventions has been further illuminated by the comprehensive virus-immune model of Boddepalli et al., which demonstrated that prophylactic IFN administration can be over 100-times more effective than post-infection treatment [76]. Their analysis revealed that even low-dose IFN (0.3 nM) administered 1-7 days before infection provides superior viral suppression compared to high-dose treatment (>10 nM) given hours after infection begins. This dramatic timing-dependence arises because early IFN primes the cellular antiviral state before viral replication establishes antagonistic countermeasures. Furthermore, their model predictions suggest that combining prophylactic IFN with direct-acting antivirals targeting viral replication or immune antagonism mechanisms could synergistically enhance therapeutic efficacy, offering a rational framework for optimizing combination therapy strategies.

Single-cell modeling approaches have provided particularly detailed insights into drug mechanisms. Teufel et al. employed single-cell poliovirus modeling to systematically characterize three distinct therapeutic approaches [81]. While all three compounds affected translation and replication organelle formation, their modeling revealed distinct mechanistic signatures: rupintrivir specifically inhibited genome synthesis, 2'-C-meA

increased RNA replicase residence time on templates, and ganetespib limited the number of RNA strands synthesized per replicase copy. Such mechanistic precision would be extremely difficult to achieve through experimental approaches alone.

HCV therapeutics have benefited extensively from modeling-guided development. Mishchenko et al. systematically compared protease inhibitors, RdRp inhibitors, and host factor inhibitors, determining that RdRp inhibition proved most effective for reducing viral RNA levels [82]. Their analysis also revealed that protease-host factor combinations achieved high effectiveness even at relatively low individual drug concentrations, suggesting promising avenues for reducing dose-related toxicities.

Perhaps the most extensively modeled antiviral is daclatasvir, an HCV NS5A inhibitor that exemplifies how computational approaches can dissect complex drug actions. Guedj et al. analyzed patient data to determine that daclatasvir simultaneously blocks RNA synthesis with 99% efficacy and particle assembly with 99.8% efficacy [83]. Subsequent modeling revealed additional temporal complexity: RNA replication inhibition dominated during early treatment phases, while assembly inhibition became more prominent later [84]. Further mechanistic studies by Quintela et al. pinpointed that daclatasvir specifically targets positive-strand synthesis, consistent with its prevention of new replicase complex formation [85].

These examples demonstrate that mechanistic models have become invaluable tools for evaluating diverse therapeutic approaches, ranging from gene therapies to small-molecule inhibitors. By enabling precise identification of optimal dosage regimens and treatment timing through *in silico* analysis, these frameworks accelerate drug development while revealing previously hidden mechanisms of action. Looking forward, integration with tissue-scale and host-level models promises to further enhance our understanding of viral infections and therapeutic interventions.

Conclusion

Despite sharing the same genomic architecture and overall replication strategies, +ssRNA viruses display diverse replication dynamics shaped by the interplay between viral strategies and host cellular environments. Mechanistic modeling has become an essential tool for linking molecular processes to observed replication behaviors and infection outcomes that influence pathogenesis and treatment response.

Computational analyses of genome allocation strategies have revealed a central evolutionary principle: the tradeoff between maximizing intracellular replication and enabling efficient virion production for cell-to-cell transmission [23]. Different viral families resolve this tension in distinct ways, consistent with their replication kinetics and transmission requirements [19, 21]. These models also highlight host ribosomes and membrane structures as critical determinants of infection outcomes and potential therapeutic targets.

In transcriptional regulation, mechanistic models have clarified the origins of RNA strand ratios, showing how initiation rates, RdRp binding, and elongation dynamics establish the characteristic asymmetries observed across viruses [19, 35, 53]. Modeling of replication modes has similarly revealed evolutionary tradeoffs: stamping machine replication provides robustness to deleterious mutations, whereas geometric replication enhances genetic diversity and adaptive potential [66]. These insights help explain viral evolutionary strategies and inform predictions of variant emergence.

Models of virus-immune interactions within the cell indicate that the timing of IFN induction, rather than its magnitude, is the primary determinant of immune-mediated clearance [30, 37]. By capturing these dynamics, computational frameworks have also guided experimental identification of specific viral antagonism mechanisms, illustrating the value of iterative model–experiment integration.

From a therapeutic perspective, evidence from multiple modeling studies converges on translation and RNA synthesis as the most effective broad-spectrum antiviral targets [21,30]. Beyond target identification, mechanistic models have dissected the actions of existing drugs, exemplified by the characterization of daclatasvir’s dual inhibition of positive-strand synthesis and particle assembly [83]. These findings underscore the role of modeling in accelerating drug development and optimizing treatment strategies.

Looking ahead, current limitations—including assumptions of fixed ribosome pools despite viral modulation of host translation [86] and the reliance on population-averaged rather than single-cell data—highlight opportunities for the next generation of models. Incorporating single-cell heterogeneity, dynamic host resource allocation, and multiscale tissue-level dynamics promises deeper insights into infection outcomes [11]. Recent advances, including spatially resolved frameworks such as the “In Silico Microscopes” model of HCV [41] and ribosome density-based modeling of EEEV [19], demonstrate how integrating geometry, diffusion, and translation dynamics can provide unprecedented mechanistic resolution. Finally, while most efforts have focused on HCV and poliovirus due to data availability, expanding mechanistic modeling to emerging viruses such as SARS-CoV-2 will enhance antiviral development and improve preparedness for future +ssRNA virus outbreaks. Mechanistic modeling thus provides not only a framework for interpreting past and present infections but also a foundation for anticipating and mitigating future +ssRNA viral threats.

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